

Gaussian Processes applied to a core calculation, a method to compress homogenized cross sections

Aurélien Chambon^{1*}, Karim Ammar¹, Frédéric Moreau¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, Gif-sur-Yvette, 91191, France

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ABSTRACT

In the context of solving the neutron transport equation on a full reactor core, homogenized cross sections (HXS) are multivariate intermediate data generated in a two-step multi-scale scheme. In the first step, HXS are computed across multiple assembly configurations. In the second step, these HXS are interpolated on the fly for core scale simulations using most often the diffusion approximation. The generation and storage of HXS represent a major bottleneck due to their high dimensionality and the large number of configurations required. Multi-Linear Interpolation (MLI) is widely used for HXS reconstruction due to its fast interpolation speed and ability to control interpolation error, at the cost of large memory footprint. Several studies have emerged to address this issue, with Multi-Output Gaussian Processes (MOGP) being one proposed solution. We present a complete comparison of MLI with MOGP on a full core reactor case, assessing three criteria: accuracy of the resulting neutron flux and k_{eff} , reconstruction speed, and memory footprint. MOGP reduces k_{eff} error by an order of magnitude on average, while reducing memory usage by a factor of 50 compared to MLI. Reconstruction speed remains competitive and presents a potential for parallelization, demonstrating MOGP's capacity to efficiently reconstruct multivariate HXS as intermediate data in large scale reactor computations.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Gaussian Processes, neutronics, APOLLO3®

1. INTRODUCTION

In reactor physics, solving the k-eigenvalue problem of the Neutron Transport Equation (NTE) is a standard computational task. However, exact solutions remain infeasible due to prohibitive computational demands in terms of time, memory, and resources. As a result, the nuclear industry relies on numerical approximations and simplified models. Among these, the two step transport-diffusion scheme as implemented in APOLLO3®[1].

A first lattice-level computation solves the NTE for individual reactor assemblies under various configurations, producing **homogenized cross sections (HXS)** that depend on key reactor parameters such as burnup, fuel temperature and moderator. In a second step, core-level computations are performed on homogenized reactor model using a diffusion approximation of the NTE, with HXS interpolated on the fly at each spatial medium based on the local core conditions. This prediction step is executed thousands of times during reactor evolution.

The generation and storage of HXS constitute a major bottleneck of the two-step scheme, often requiring several to hundreds of gigabytes of memory. However, due to the large number of required predictions, the computational cost of HXS evaluation becomes a critical factor. **Fast and memory-efficient prediction methods are therefore essential to maintain efficiency in large-scale reactor simulations.**

*aurelien.chambon@cea.fr

With the recent democratisation of Machine Learning, numerous studies have emerged to address this computational bottleneck. Various methods have been proposed to efficiently represent HXS, including Polynomial regression/interpolation[2, 3], Splines, kernel methods[4] and artificial neural network[5, 6, 7].

The use of **Multi-Output Gaussian Processes (MOGP)**, particularly the Linear Model of Coregionalization (LMC), for HXS representation in [8] is promising. Unlike standard interpolation methods, MOGP leverages the strong correlations and redundancies across different HXS, enabling high compression with a small number of support points. It provides predictive variance, offering confidence estimates for uncertainty quantification. Furthermore, inference is computationally efficient, making it well-suited for core calculations. These advantages make MOGP a viable candidate for HXS representation.

While MOGP has demonstrated its potential in reactor physics, it has not yet been applied in full reactor core simulations. In this work, we integrated HXS reconstruction using MOGP in the APOLLO3® code and compare it with the widely used **Multi-Linear Interpolation (MLI)** in a full reactor core computation. MLI is known for its ability to control interpolation error and its fast evaluation time.

The study is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of MOGP, with a focus on the Lazy-LMC variant used in this work. Section 3 details the methodology, including data preprocessing and the training procedures. Section 4 presents a **comparative analysis of MOGP and MLI based on three criteria: accuracy of the resulting flux and k_{eff} computation, reconstruction speed, and memory footprint**. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study and outlines future directions.

2. MULTI-OUTPUT GAUSSIAN PROCESSES

Section 2.1 provides a brief overview of single-output Gaussian Processes to facilitate understanding of Multi-Output Gaussian Processes (MOGP). Section 2.2 introduces the Lazy-LMC, the MOGP model of interest in this work.

2.1. Gaussian Processes

Gaussian Processes can be introduced in multiple ways[9]. One perspective is to view them as a probabilistic generalization of kernel ridge regression. For a more rigorous definition :

Let \mathcal{X} be a set of points (often a subset of \mathbb{R}^d). A Gaussian process is a collection of random variables $\{f(\mathbf{x}) : \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}\}$ such that, for any finite choice of points $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n \in \mathcal{X}$, the random vector $(f(\mathbf{x}_1), f(\mathbf{x}_2), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_n))$ follows a multivariate normal distribution.

This distribution is characterized by a mean function $m(\mathbf{x})$ and a covariance function $k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$:

$$\begin{aligned} m(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x})], \\ k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') &= \text{Cov}[f(\mathbf{x}), f(\mathbf{x}')] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

To estimate the process at an unobserved point \mathbf{x}_* , we express the joint probability of the known observations and the unknown value $f(\mathbf{x}_*)$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f(\mathcal{X}) \\ f(\mathbf{x}_*) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} m(\mathcal{X}) \\ m(\mathbf{x}_*) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} k(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{X}) + \sigma^2 I & k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathcal{X}) \\ k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathcal{X}) & k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_*) \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (2)$$

We then obtain the conditional distribution of $f(\mathbf{x}_*)$, which is Gaussian with mean and covariance given by (here in the case where $m(\cdot) = 0$):

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x}_*) | \mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{X}, f(\mathbf{X})] &= k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{X}) [k(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \sigma^2 I]^{-1} f(\mathbf{X}) \\ \text{Cov}[f(\mathbf{x}_*) | \mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{X}, f(\mathbf{X})] &= k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{x}_*) - k(\mathbf{x}_*, \mathbf{X}) [k(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}) + \sigma^2 I]^{-1} k(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{x}_*)\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

If one examines the mean of this conditional distribution, one obtains the prediction formula identical to that derived in standard kernel ridge regression. One can note that, in an offline phase, one can precompute the inverse of the kernel matrix and its product with the training outputs $f(\mathcal{X})$. During prediction, we only need to compute the covariance between the test points and the training inputs, then multiply by the precomputed term which enables efficient inference without re-evaluating the full training data.

2.2. Multi-Output Gaussian Process

In the context of HXS, we aim to predict a large set of cross sections that are not independent but exhibit strong correlations. This motivates the use of Multi-Output Gaussian Processes, which extend standard Gaussian Processes to handle multiple correlated outputs.

MOGPs model both correlations in the input space and dependencies between outputs through a joint covariance function. This implies defining a correlation structure across distinct outputs. The most straightforward and widely-used framework for this is the Linear Model of Co-regionalization (LMC), in which each output is expressed as a linear combination of a small number of shared latent Gaussian Processes, each with its own covariance function:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^q H_{i,j} u_j(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon_i, \quad u_j \sim \mathcal{GP}(0, k_j), \quad \epsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2 I), \quad \forall i \in [1, p] \quad (4)$$

For more details on MOGPs and the LMC model, the reader is referred to [10].

Each task or HXS is modeled as a linear combination of q latent Gaussian processes. The matrix H , noise terms σ_i , and kernel k_j parameters are optimized during training.

Unfortunately, if performed naively, the computational cost of this approach grows cubically with the number of outputs and data points. Several simplifications or approximations have therefore been developed to circumvent this issue. In [8], it has been shown that the training-free Lazy-LMC is sufficient for representing HXS. A parameter-free spline kernel of degree 2 is used. A principal component analysis (PCA) is performed on the HXS, and the first q principal components are retained to construct the matrix H without optimization. The noise is assumed isotropic and fixed by the user, $\sigma_i = \sigma$. Since HXS are computed rather than measured, they are inherently noise-free, a small noise level $\sigma = 10^{-8}$ is sufficient to ensure numerical stability.

For these reasons, we adopted this model for the study. Although the Lazy-LMC does not require hyper-parameter optimization, the choice of q is critical for both accuracy and effective dimensionality reduction.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we examine the methodology used in the study, focusing on data generation and pre-processing, which are essential for training MOGP.

3.1. Generation and pre-processing of the data

As mentioned earlier, one of the key advantages of Gaussian Processes is their ability to represent smooth functions with a small number of training points. For instance, in this benchmark, we built our

Cartesian MLI grid using 7650 lattice calculations, while training our MOGP required only 256 points. The key challenge is choosing representative points to construct the MOGP training set. To achieve this, we applied a squared root on the burnup axis and we used Sobol sequence for our sampling as recommended in [8].

The preprocessing consists of multiple steps that significantly influence the model quality. First, constant HXS are removed and we eliminate low-burnup regions exhibiting irregularities. We finally normalize parameters and cross sections to avoid bias from high-magnitude values.

3.2. Generation of the models

As discussed in Section 2.2, we retained the Lazy-LMC model. Although no training is required, the choice of the number of latent functions q is critical. To determine an appropriate q , we perform a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) on the normalized training set, and we use the cumulative explained variance to determine an optimal rank q .

3.3. Tools

The entire workflow is divided into an offline phase implemented in Python, and the online phase implemented in C++. The offline phase includes the parsing of homogenized cross-sections (HXS), preprocessing, model training, and testing implemented within a dedicated Python module named `GaussianHandler`. This framework leverages standard scientific libraries: including Pandas for data handling, PyTorch[11] for tensor operations, and a library developed in [8] base on GPyTorch[12] for Gaussian process modeling.

The online module reconstructs on the fly HXS in the APOLLO3® core solver. A key advantage of MOGP is that predictions reduce to simple linear algebra operations, such as matrix-matrix or matrix-vector products, that can be efficiently accelerated using highly optimized and vectorized libraries. This property motivated the implementation of the reconstruction module in C++ within APOLLO3®, using the Intel Math Kernel Library (MKL) ensuring efficiency.

4. RESULTS

This section presents a comparative evaluation of MOGP and MLI based on three key criteria: precision, speed of reconstruction, and compression rate.

4.1. Physical context

In this study, we compare MLI and MOGP on a large unrodded PWR core with heavy reflector and homogenized cells, using the APOLLO3® MINOS diffusion solver. The HXS describe a fission chain with 11 isotopes (Xe–Sm), 2 energy groups, and 4 parameters: burnup, fuel temperature, moderator temperature, and boron concentration. Multiple fuel assembly designs are used to model the core.

We define three disjoint sets: \mathcal{M}_{Ref} , 1000 parameter points sampled for which lattice calculations are performed, and used as reference. \mathcal{M}_{MOGP} , 256 points sampled with the method described in Section 3.1, and used to train MOGP models. \mathcal{M}_{MLI} , 7650 points forming a Cartesian grid, used for MLI interpolation. The sets are mutually exclusive, ensuring no overlap in sampled points.

We trained a separate MOGP model per material (per cell in our setup) in the core region. While we opted to use MLI instead of MOGP for reflector regions, due to the simplicity of the reflector grid.

The comparison on the full reactor core is conducted as follows: for each point in \mathcal{M}_{Ref} , we perform three full core computations: in each case, the parameters of every cell in every assembly are set to the corresponding values from the reference lattice calculation, then we compare the results across the three runs (Reference, MLI and MOGP). Therefore, the Reference core calculation uses exact HXS, MLI

uses interpolated HXS based on the parameter values, and MOGP predicts HXS based on the same parameters.

4.2. Precision

The criterion analyzed in this section is precision. While the accuracy of the HXS reconstruction can be directly evaluated against the reference, the study assesses it within the context of concrete core computations.

Figure 1. The upper plot displays $|k_{eff}^{Ref} - k_{eff}^{MOGP}|$ in blue and $|k_{eff}^{Ref} - k_{eff}^{MLI}|$ in red as a function of the global burnup. The lower plot displays $\max_{i \in \{Cells\}} (\frac{P_i^{Ref} - P_i^{MOGP}}{P_i^{Ref}})$ in blue and $\max_{i \in \{Cells\}} (\frac{P_i^{Ref} - P_i^{MLI}}{P_i^{Ref}})$ in red as a function of the global burnup. At fixed burnup, multiple parameter points in \mathcal{M}_{Ref} explain the mean and spread observed in the plot.

Figure 1, shows the error of the MLI and MOGP cases relative to the reference. For clarity, the plots display the average error and standard deviation as a function of burnup on the x-axis. Regarding k_{eff} , MOGP reduces on average the error by a factor of 10 compared to MLI (see Figure 1). A similar trend is observed in the standard deviation of the error. Although not shown in Figure 1, the maximum error in k_{eff} is 68 pcm for MOGP and 97 pcm for MLI. The MLI error remains within the specified bound of 100 pcm, as the Cartesian grid was designed for assembly calculations with this constraint. This criterion resulted in a grid with 7650 points, which can be refined to improve accuracy, at the cost of increased lattice calculation and memory usage.

The maximum error in power shows a similar trend to that of k_{eff} , though less pronounced. An overshoot in the MOGP error is observed between 8000 and 10000 $MWdt^{-1}$, likely due to the gadolinium peak. This could be mitigated by increasing the number of training points in that region. Despite this, the errors remain within acceptable limits for core computation purposes.

Figure 2. density of $k_{eff}^{Ref} - k_{eff}^{MOGP}$ in blue and $k_{eff}^{Ref} - k_{eff}^{MLI}$ in red.

An interesting characteristic of MOGP is shown in Figure 2. The error distribution is centered around zero for MOGP, in contrast to MLI. This is significant in the context of core computation, as MOGP does not introduce a systematic bias, unlike MLI. The biased behavior of MLI can be justified by the convex or concave nature of HXS, which leads MLI to consistently over- or under-estimate them. The Gaussian behavior of MOGP can explain the absence of bias in the error.

Overall, MOGP demonstrates excellent precision, consistent with the machine learning analysis presented in [8]. For MOGP to be a viable candidate, the reconstruction time must be competitive with the rate at which data can be compressed and stored.

4.3. Speed of reconstruction

The algorithmic complexity of the reconstruction provides insight into its scalability. Let p denote the number of parameters of the HXS, N_{xs} the number of HXS to reconstruct, N_{mil} the number of media or point sets for reconstruction, and N_{lat} the number of latent functions in the Lazy-LMC model. Assuming $N_{xs} \gg$ number of training points, the complexity scales as $2^p N_{xs} N_{mil}$ for MLI and $N_{lat} N_{xs} N_{mil}$ for the Lazy-LMC model. For the Lazy-LMC to be competitive, we require $2^p \approx N_{lat}$. In our case, $2^p = 16$ and $N_{lat} \approx 20$. Importantly, the complexity of Lazy-LMC and MOGP models does not grow exponentially with p , unlike MLI. This property makes MOGP particularly well-suited for high-dimensional HXS reconstruction.

Table I. Time of HXS reconstruction

Number of mediums	MLI (s)	MOGP (s)
5×10^4	0.370	0.227
1×10^5	0.751	0.491
5×10^5	3.670	2.440

Table I reports the reconstruction time for macroscopic cross sections on a single CPU thread for vary-

ing numbers of media. Although the algorithmic complexity suggests that Lazy-LMC should perform slightly worse than MLI, the observed behavior is reversed. This can be explained by the fact that MOGP reconstruction benefits from the highly optimized, vectorized nature of its linear algebra operations. As a result, the actual performance gains from hardware acceleration and algorithmic structure outweigh the theoretical complexity prediction, demonstrating the practical advantage of MOGP in real-world implementations.

4.4. Compression rates

The final criterion of comparison is memory footprint. Table II presents the compression ratio ($\frac{Size_{MLI}}{Size_{MOGP}}$) of the MOGP model for two configurations: 11 isotopes with 2 energy groups and 20 energy groups. The achieved compression ratios are already significant, though further improvement is possible through optimized model storage. Beyond the compression ratio, as previously noted, MOGP reduces the number of lattice calculations required to accurately represent the HXS, leading to lower computational demands during lattice calculation.

Table II. Compression rate: $\frac{Size_{MLI}}{Size_{MOGP}}$

MLI	MOGP 2G	MOGP 20G
1	50	120

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms within a full core calculation the claims previously put forward in [13]. MOGP shows a strong competitiveness over MLI in a full-core reactor calculations, excelling across precision, reconstruction speed, and memory efficiency. MOGP reduces on average k_{eff} error by a factor of 10 compared to MLI at a 50× memory compression ratio, with comparable or superior flux reconstruction accuracy. Moreover, MOGP exhibits lower error bias and requires fewer training points to accurately reconstruct high-fidelity homogenized cross sections.

The use of MOGP leads to significant reduction in costly lattice calculations. Beyond the evaluated metrics, MOGP offers additional advantages, such as uncertainty quantification via predictive variance, support for adaptive sampling, and robust model validation through leave-one-out techniques and outlier detection. Future work must extend validation to diverse reactor cores and benchmark configurations to confirm generalizability and robustness. Additionally, MOGP should be extended to full core evolution and concentration reconstruction.

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